

COMPLICATIONS IN THE OPERATION OF GAS AND GAS CONDENSATE WELLS

Salamat Xojamuratov

Master student of Karakalpak State University

Tel: +99890 652 01 92 khojamuratovsalamat@gmail.com

Shahlo Oripova

basic doctoral student, Karshi Engineering and Economic Institute

Bobirzhon Adizov

Doctor of Technical Sciences, Leading Researcher of the Laboratory "Colloid Chemistry and Industrial Ecology" of the Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7614100>

Abstract: This article discusses the complications in the operation of gas and gas condensate fields, including the formation of bottom water cones, flooding of the bottomhole zone of the well, destruction of the bottomhole zone of the well, sanding of the productive formation, hydrate formation, gas passage between pipe joints, aggressive action of hydrogen sulfide and carbon dioxide .

Key words: Complications, formation of bottom water cones, sanding, destruction of the bottomhole zone, flooding of the bottomhole zone, carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulfide, hydrate formation, foaming agent, surfactant, inhibitor.

Аннотация: В данной работе рассмотрены осложнения при эксплуатации газовых и газоконденсатных месторождений, в том числе образование конусов подошвенной воды, обводнение призабойной зоны скважины, разрушение призабойной зоны скважины, пескопроявление, гидратообразование, прохождение газа между стыками труб, агрессивное действие сероводорода и углекислого газа на эксплуатационную колонну и насосно-компрессорные трубы.

Ключевые слова: осложнения, образование конусов подошвенной воды, пескопроявление, разрушение призабойной зоны, обводнение призабойной зоны, углекислый газ, сероводород, гидратообразование, пенообразователь, поверхностно-активные вещества, ингибитор.

Introduction. During the operation of gas and gas condensate fields, there are many factors that limit the flow rate of gas and gas condensate wells. These consequences during the operation of gas and gas condensate wells lead to well productivity. Their accounting during the operation of gas and gas condensate wells allows you to correctly determine the technological modes of operation of the wells, to correctly conduct production.

Literature review. Many scientists conducted scientific research on the exploitation of gas and gas condensate fields. As a result of research by I.R. Yushkov, G.P. Khizhnyak, P.Yu. Ilyushin, F.A. Trebin, Yu.F. Makogon, K.S. Basniev, N.R. Akopyan, G.A. Zotov, Z.S. Aliev, L.V. Samuylova, B.P. Gvozdev, A.I. Gritsenko, A.E. Kornilov, A.F. Beznosikov, M.I. Zaboeva, I.A. Sintsov, D.A. Ostapchuk, A.Kh. Mirzajanzade, O.L. Kuznetsov, K.S. Basniev, A.I. Gritsenko, O.M. Ermilov, R.I. Shamov, I.V. Strizhak, T.A. Gunkina and other scientists solved many issues related to the exploitation of gas and gas condensate fields.

Research methodology. When developing gas fields, there are many factors that limit the flow rates of gas and gas condensate wells (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Complications in the operation of gas and gas condensate wells

Analysis and results. The formation of bottom water cones or premature breakthrough of edge water into the well can reduce the permeability of the bottomhole zone and even stop the flow of gas into the well.

Watering of the bottomhole zone leads to such negative consequences as a decrease in well flow rate, severe watering of gas, and hence a large volume of its separation in the fields to separate water, the risk of formation of a large volume of crystalline hydrates, etc. The main complication in the development of fields that have switched to falling production, as well as newly commissioned fields with low reservoir productivity, the upward gas flow rate is insufficient for liquid removal. This contributes to the accumulation of fluid in the wellbore

and at the bottom of the wells, which leads to a decrease in their productivity, and sometimes to their complete stop.

The choice of moisture removal method depends on many factors. At low gas flow rates from the well, it is sufficient to use one of the periodic methods for removing moisture, and for high flow rates, one of the continuous methods. To remove fluid from the well, apply: continuous removal; periodic removal (Fig. 2).

Fig 2. Fluid removal from wells

Destruction of the bottomhole zone due to the removal of sand particles and cementing material of the rock due to excessively large pressure gradients at the bottomhole during its operation. There are three possible options for avoiding rock failure:

Maintaining a minimum gradient less than its allowed value;

The use of a mechanical method of fastening the bottom of the well;

Application of the chemical method of fixing the bottom of the well [4].

The effect of sand plug on well productivity is almost identical to the effect of well imperfection in terms of formation penetration [5].

Sand intrusion of a productive formation. At the same time, sand plugs, which are hardly permeable to gas, are formed at the bottom of the well, significantly reducing the flow rate of the wells. The destruction of the rock skeleton and the removal of rock particles to the bottomhole are due to the excess of pressure gradients in the bottomhole zone over the allowable ones. The accumulation of sand plug at the bottom reduces the flow rate of the well and can lead to various disturbances, for example, sticking of the well pipes. Removal of moisture from the bottomhole zone of sandy-argillaceous productive formations will help reduce the filtration resistance to gas inflow, increase the production rate while reducing drawdown on the formation [6].

Table 2

Fighting the formation of sand plugs in gas wells	
By restricting gas extraction	
	The removal of sand entering the bottomhole through the wellbore to the surface
	Periodic removal of sand plugs by various methods
	The use of downhole filters of various designs
	Fastening of the bottomhole zone with various cementing compositions

Hydration. Natural gases, which are a mixture of various components, at certain pressures and temperatures in the presence of water form white crystalline substances called hydrates. From the components of natural gases, hydrates independently form: methane, ethane, propane, isobutane, nitrogen, carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulfide, and mercaptans [5].

The main factors determining the conditions for hydrate formation are gas pressure, its temperature, and the presence of water [9]. The fight against hydrates, as well as with any deposits, is carried out in the direction of their prevention and elimination. Hydrate prevention methods should always be preferred. It is easier and cheaper to prevent hydrate formation than to eliminate already formed and accumulated hydrates. Methods to prevent the formation of hydrates are divided into three groups (Fig. 3.):

Fig. 3. Hydrate Prevention Methods

Aggressive action of hydrogen sulfide and carbon dioxide. Risk of destruction of the production string, production pipes and surface equipment due to corrosion or erosion. In the presence of carbon dioxide CO₂, hydrogen sulfide H₂S and other corrosion causative agents at certain values of humidity, temperature and flow rates, intensive destruction of pipes is possible. In some fields, especially at high well flow rates, erosive destruction of pipes, fittings, and equipment can occur, since at high gas flow rates, the destructive ability of solid particles moving with gas becomes significant.

The intensity of corrosion depends on the pressure and temperature of the medium, the concentration of aggressive components in the gas, the amount of moisture in the well production, the characteristics of the metals of the downhole and field equipment, the design of the well, the degree and nature of water mineralization, the composition of the condensate, the mode of movement of the gas-liquid flow, etc. [5]. Table 2

Methods for protecting pipes and equipment from corrosion	
	Inhibition with corrosion inhibitor substances
	Application for equipment alloyed corrosion-resistant steels and alloys
	The use of electrochemical methods of corrosion protection: cathodic and sacrificial protection
	Application of corrosion-resistant non-metallic and metallic coatings
	Use of special technological modes of equipment operation

There are several ways to use inhibitors in a well: injection of inhibitors into the annular space of wells, injection of inhibitors into the reservoir, injection of solid inhibitors. The supply of inhibitors into the annulus is carried out using an inhibitor unit. A metered amount of the inhibitor is constantly

supplied under the action of its own weight to the bottom of the well through the annular space, from where the inhibitor is transported to the surface by an ascending gas flow along the walls of the flow pipes [10]. The experience of operating wells in the fields of hydrogen sulfide-containing gas shows that typical well designs can be used in single-layer fields [11].

Passage of gas between pipe joints. During the operation of gas wells, the problem of gas passage between pipe joints is in the focus of attention of industrial and research organizations. The presence of pressure between the pipe joints leads to a disruption in the normal operation of the well system and the formation of griffins, as well as to accidents associated with the rupture of the reinforcing pipe joints.

Causes of gas leakage between pipe joints Gas ingress into the gaps between pipe joints is caused by: • mortise joints of joints of reinforcing pipes; • sealing ring for connecting reinforcing pipes in the upper part of the head; • leakage of the cement ring behind the working joint of the pipes. Gas leakage leads to its ascent through the annulus between the operational and technical pipe joints, uncontrolled gas flow into the unproductive formation and critical pressure on the well.

Conclusions and recommendation. In conclusion, we can say that taking into account the complications in the operation of gas and gas condensate wells allows you to correctly determine the technological modes of well operation, correctly conduct production, achieve well productivity and comply with the requirements of underground protection.

1. Wells penetrating formations with bottom water are recommended to be operated while maintaining the maximum anhydrous flow rate.

2. The accumulation of fluid in the wellbore and at the bottom of the wells leads to a decrease in their productivity and their complete stop.

3. When justifying the technological mode of operation in the conditions of destruction of the bottomhole formation zone, it is necessary to use technologies that exclude the destruction of unstable reservoirs.

4. The fight against the formation of sand plugs in gas wells can be carried out by limiting gas extraction, forced removal of sand entering the bottomhole through the wellbore to the surface, as well as using bottomhole filters of various designs, fixing the bottomhole zone with various compositions.

5. Gas heating prevents the formation of hydrates, but is effective only within the field, since the gas cools rapidly when moving through pipelines. The

most effective method for the prevention and elimination of formed hydrates is the supply of various inhibitors of hydrate formation to gas pipelines.

6. The presence of pressure between pipe joints leads to disruption of the normal operation of the well system and the formation of griffins, as well as to accidents associated with rupture of reinforcing pipe joints.

7. The use of corrosion inhibitors is the most common method. The experience of operating wells in the fields of hydrogen sulfide-containing gas shows that typical well designs can be used in single-layer fields.

Literature:

1. Ilyushin P.Yu. Khizhnyak G.P, Yushkov I.R, "Development and operation of oil and gas fields": Study method. allowance / - Perm: Publishing House of Perm. National Research Polytechnic University, 2013. - 177 p.

2. Basniev K.S. Makogon Yu.F., Trebin F.A., "Production of natural gas". - M.: Nedra, 1976. - 368 p.

3. N.R. Akopyan "Temporary instructions for removing fluid from gas and gas condensate wells using foaming agents." SO ASSR, Stavropol, 1977 - 23 p.

4. Aliyev Z.S, Zotov G.A. "Instruction for the comprehensive study of gas and gas condensate reservoirs and wells" // M., Nedra, 1980 - 301 p.

5. Aliev Z.S., Samuylova L.V. "Gas hydrodynamic studies of gas and gas condensate reservoirs and wells": Textbook for universities. - M.: MAKS Press, 2011. - 340 p.

6. Gritsenko A.I., Gvozdev B.P., Kornilov A.E. "Operation of gas and gas condensate fields": Reference manual. - M.: Nedra, 1988. - 575 p.

7. Beznosikov A.F., Ostapchuk D.A, Sintsov I.A., Zaboeva M.I. "Development and operation of gas and gas condensate fields": Textbook. - Tyumen: TIU, 2016. - 80 p.

8. Aliev Z.S. Basniev K.S., Kuznetsov O.L., Mirzajanzade A.Kh., "Fundamentals of gas production technology". - M., Nedra, 2003. - 880 p.

9. "Rules for the development of gas and gas condensate fields" Moscow, Nedra, 1971 - 104 p.

10. Aliev Z.S., Ermilov O.M., Gritsenko A.I., Remizov V.V., Zotov G.A. "Guidelines for the study of wells". M., Nauka, 1995 - 523 p.

11. Shamov R.I., Strizhak I.V., Yakovlev K.G. and others. "Well equipment for the production of gas containing aggressive components", M., VNIIEGazprom, 1974. - 28 p.